

SPATIAL

BUILDING THE PATHWAY TOWARD A TRUSTWORTHY EUROPEAN CYBERSECURITY SECTOR

Education and
Skills Building

New Business
Models

Transparency and
Explainability

Resilience and
Privacy

Societal Impact
for Uptake

4 USE CASES

Privacy-preserving AI
on the Edge and
beyond.

Improving
explainability,
resilience and
performance of
cybersecurity
analysis of 5G/4G/IoT
networks

Accountable AI in
Emergency eCall
System

Resilient
Cybersecurity
Analytics.

SPATIAL is a consortium led by TU Delft, consisting of 12 partners from 8 EU member states

Funded by
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